

SELECTIVE LASER SINTERING FOR MANUFACTURING OF EXFOLIATED GRAPHITE NANOPATELETS/POLYAMIDIE12 MULTIFUNCTIONAL NANOCOMPOSITES

M. Karevan¹, Sh. Eshraghi¹, S. Das^{1,2}, K. Kalaitzidou^{1,2*}

¹ G. W. Woodruff School of Mechanical Engineering, ² School of Materials Science and Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, USA

* Corresponding author (kyriaki.kalaitzidou@me.gatech.edu)

Keywords: *nanocomposites, graphite nanoplatelets, selective laser sintering, polyamide12*

1 Introduction

Selective laser sintering (SLS), an additive manufacturing method, is increasingly being considered in fabrication of polymer nanocomposites (PNCs) [1, 2]. The main advantages compared to traditional polymer or polymer composite fabrication methods are that SLS allows for i) parts with complex geometry without the need of expensive tooling like molds, ii) functionally graded PNCs i.e., composition and properties of the composites vary along the part thickness, and iii) greater control of nanomaterial dispersion and alignment [3].

The intrinsic properties mainly thermal conductivity of nanomaterials and the thermal properties of the polymer significantly affect the sintering process [4, 5]. Moreover, the SLS process requires that the polymer powder is uniformly coated with the nanomaterials which is not easily achieved with commonly used compounding methods such as melt mixing, shear pulverization, etc. [6, 1, 7]. Furthermore, preparation of the composite powder with an appropriate particle size and morphology is critical because the compounding not only affects the final characteristics such as dimensional accuracy and of porosity level, but it also dictates the processing ability of the composite particularly in additive processes [8]. Therefore, SLS processed polymer nanocomposites do not exhibit the performance required for composites at high-end applications. For instance, a recent work reports the use of solid state mixing for preparation of the SLS powder for SLS processing of carbon black (CB)/PA12 composites. It has been demonstrated that the composites prepared by SLS had an electrical conductivity several orders of magnitude greater than the conductivity of the corresponding composites made by melt-mixing and injection molding (IM) [9, 1]. However, the observations have revealed that the SLS parts had a lower modulus and

strength compared to the melt-mixed parts due to presence of CB aggregates and porosity in the CB/PA12 parts [10].

This study demonstrates fabrication of multifunctional PNCs with improved mechanical and electrical properties using SLS. Mechanical properties including tensile behavior and impact resistance of sintered PNCs were determined and compared with those of PNCs made by IM process as baseline. Positive effects specific to SLS in enhanced mechanical and electrical properties of the PNCs were observed and discussed. Moreover, a lower electrical percolation threshold and anisotropic electrical performance were observed for the SLS-processed PNCs compared to the injection molded ones indicating ability of SLS to fabricate multifunctional PNCs with enhanced mechanical and electrical properties.

2 Materials

PA12 powder (VESTOSINT® X 1553 white, Evonik Industries, Essen, Germany) with average diameter of 50-100 μm and T_m in the range of 176-184°C was used as the base polymer. Exfoliated graphite nanoplatelets (GNP) from XG Sciences, with an average diameter of $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ and thickness of 10-20 nm were used as the nanomaterial.

3 Fabrication of Nanocomposites

In this study, the composites were made using a two-step process: i) compounding nanomaterial and matrix, and ii) forming/shaping using SLS and injection molding (IM) as a reference process. The compounding method used is the coating method reported in our previous study [11] to prepare the starting SLS powder. The PA12 powder was coated with 3 and 5wt% GNP. As-received GNP was mixed in isopropyl alcohol (IPA) using ultrasonic energy (UIP500hd, Hielscher USA) for 45 min with

amplitudes of 80% and manual mixing of the neat PA12 powder in the solution. The solution of the nanocomposite powder was filtered and the residual coated powder was then thoroughly dried in a vacuum oven at 100 °C for 10 hrs to minimize the hydrolytic degradation. The GNP/PA12 compound was kept in sealed containers to avoid degradation of the material upon contact with the air moisture. Neat PA12 parts were laser sintered as reference.

A Sinterstation® 2000 commercial SLS machine (3D Systems Inc., Valencia, CA) was used to process the GNP-coated PA12 powder prepared by the coating method. A sieve shaker was used before the SLS process to eliminate the agglomerates and to provide the coated PA12 with more uniform grain size. The parameters used, which maximized the tensile strength of 5wt% GNP/PA12 composites and yielded the SLS parts with good geometric accuracy and density are: laser power of 8.5 W, laser scan speed and spacing of 762 mm/s and 152.4 µm respectively, part-side temperature set-point of 171 °C (PA12) and 170 °C (PNCs) and powder feed temperature set-point of 100 °C. The process was operated at a roller speed of 76.2 mm/s, powder layer thickness of 101.6 µm and piston temperature of 135 °C.

The GNP-coated PA12 powder prepared by the coating method described earlier was fed into a DSM Micro 15cc Compounder (vertical, co-rotating twin-screw micro extruder) followed by IM. The processing parameters used were $T_{\text{barrel}} = 190$ °C, screw speed of 60 and 100 rpm for 1 and 2 min, respectively, $T_{\text{mold}} = 80$ °C and a pressure of ~750 KPa. The optimal processing parameters were chosen as those that maximized the flexural properties and impact resistance of the fabricated GNP/PA12 PNCs since these properties remarkably define the level of nanomaterial agglomeration and thus quality of load transfer at the nanomaterial-polymer interface.

4 Characterization of Nanocomposites

The tensile properties of the specimens were determined according to ASTM D638 using an Instron 33R 4466 apparatus with a 500 N load cell and an extensometer (Instron 2630-101) with a gage length of 10 mm. A displacement control with a velocity of 2.54 mm/s was applied. The impact resistance of the specimens was determined according to ASTM D256 using an Izod pendulum test. Each data point reported is an average of five repetitions.

The thermomechanical behavior was studied by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA, Q800, TA Instruments) using the single cantilever mode at oscillation amplitude of 0.015 mm and a fixed frequency of 1 Hz. The composites were heated from ambient temperature to 150 °C at a heating rate of 5 °C/min. Modulated differential scanning calorimetry (MDSC) work was performed on a DSC Q2000 (TA Instruments, New Castle, Delaware, USA) using specimens of about 7-10 mg. Nitrogen was used for purging. Measurements were performed from the equilibrate temperature of -30 °C to 200 °C at a heating rate of 3 °C/min.

Electrical conductivity measurements were made with a Solartron 1260 coupled with a 1296 Dielectric Interface using 0.1 Vac for frequencies ranging from 10 MHz down to 10⁻² Hz at room temperature. The morphology of the composites was studied with a Zeiss DSM 940A scanning electron microscope (SEM) operating at 5 kV accelerating voltage. Prior to the SEM study the fracture surface was gold-coated to minimize the charging effects during the SEM observations.

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 Mechanical Behavior of PNCs

- Tensile Behavior

The tensile modulus and strength of SLS and IM made GNP/PA12 composites at GNP loading of 0, 3 and 5 wt% GNP are shown in Table 1. The results clearly demonstrate that: i) SLS processing of neat PA12 dramatically improves both the strength and the modulus compared to the corresponding properties of IM made PA12 parts, ii) addition of GNP in PA12 enhances the strength and modulus of neat PA12 in case of IM. In contrary, it is observed that when SLS is used addition of GNP enhances the modulus but not the strength. Specifically, addition of 3 wt% GNP in PA12 results in the greatest modulus enhancement both in SLS and IM processed composites with 48% and 22% enhancement in modulus respectively compare to that of the neat PA12 processed similarly.

The reduction in tensile modulus of SLS composites at 5wt% GNP and the lack of strength enhancement are correlated to unavoidable GNP aggregation that acts against the reinforcing ability of GNP. As the GNP content increases, GNP interferes with the sintering process masking the polymer powder leading to variations in energy doses delivered to the PA12 powder and thus the sintering of PA12. The

tensile strength is sensitive to the dispersion state of nanomaterials as reported in literature [12, 13] so it is speculated that IM made composites exhibit better dispersion/distribution of GNP during processing.

- Impact Resistance

The impact strength of GNP/PA12 composites, presented in Table 1, is significantly affected by the manufacturing method and GNP content. It is clearly shown that the impact strength of composites made by IM monotonously increases with GNP content. However when SLS is used the impact strength of the composites decreases with addition of GNP. It is noted that the manufacturing method had no significant effect on the impact strength of the neat PA12. The decrease in the impact strength of SLS composites is maybe due to GNP absorbing part of the laser energy and thus reducing the energy available to locally melt the PA12 particles and inter-diffuse their boundaries resulting thus in structures that can absorb less energy before fracture is reached. This structure may promote crack propagation along boundaries of imperfectly sintered PA12 grains and thus reduction of the impact resistance. The results are in agreement with those reported elsewhere [6, 14, 12].

To better understand effect of sintering on the observed mechanical properties, the correlation among thermomechanical properties including the glass transition temperature (T_g), melting phenomena and morphology of fabricated PNCs was assessed.

5.2 Melting Behavior of Nanocomposites

The heat flow thermograms were obtained by DSC during the melting transition of the GNP/PA12 composites made by SLS or IM. Table 2 represents the dependence of the heat of fusion during melting transition on the manufacturing method and GNP content. The corresponding degree of crystallinity, calculated using equation (1), is shown in Table 2.

$$\chi\% = \frac{\Delta H}{\Delta H_m^\circ \left(1 - \frac{wt\%}{100}\right)} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$\Delta H_m^\circ = 209.3$ J/g was used as the theoretical heat of melting for a 100% crystalline PA12 [15]. It is demonstrated that the degree of crystallinity of neat PA12 increases by 18% when SLS is used which may explain the observed difference in mechanical properties of the SLS and IM neat PA12. It is clearly

shown that the degree of crystallinity decreases with addition of GNP regardless of the manufacturing method used. The results suggest the presence of a secondary mechanism, the reduction in the degree of crystallinity, which counteracts the main reinforcing mechanism induced by stiffening effect of high modulus GNP that is responsible for the enhancement of tensile modulus. The hypothesis is that presence of GNP also alters the dynamics of polymer chains surrounding the nanomaterials and thus the structure and properties of the polymer chains at or near the GNP surface. The thermomechanical properties are used to study the changes in the polymer chain mobilization and can be utilized in order to understand the relationship between local properties such as glass transition of the polymer and macro-scale properties of the composites.[16, 17].

5.3 Viscoelastic Properties

Interfacial interactions dictate the load transfer mechanisms at the GNP-PA12 interface and thus the macro-scale properties of polymer composites and can lead to immobilization of the polymer chains at the GNP surface. In case of SLS processing the confinement effect of GNP on polymer segments may interfere with consolidation [5]. The interfacial interactions and their correlation to the macro-scale properties of the composites were assessed using DMA. The $\tan\delta$ and the T_g of the GNP/PA12 composites made by either SLS or IM as a function of GNP content are shown in Table 2. SLS processing results in both neat PA12 and GNP/PA12 composites with higher T_g than the corresponding counterparts made by IM. Addition of GNP however did not affect the T_g of SLS processed composites. On the contrary, addition of GNP had positive effect on T_g and moved T_g toward higher temperatures in case of IM processing. The observed changes in T_g are related to the competing effects of i) GNP and hard PA12 crystallites, ii) GNP aggregation, and iii) porous structure and residues of unmelted PA12 powder, specific to the SLS process, that has negative effect on T_g [18, 17].

As shown in Table 2, $\tan\delta$ of both the neat PA12 and the GNP/PA12 composites significantly decreases across the temperature regime investigated when SLS is used and when GNP is added. The observed results indicate that the energy damping ability is compromised, which is in agreement with the observed decrease in impact strength, and the enhancement of the elastic behavior. It is noted that,

in addition to the compromise of the damping ability, the degree of crystallinity also decreases upon addition of GNP, significantly more in case of SLS processed composites, although it still remains higher than the degree of crystallinity of their IM counterparts. Therefore, it is concluded that a rigid interfacial region is formed that consists mainly of immobilized amorphous polymer chains.

5.4 Electrical Properties of PNCs: SLS v.s. IM

Fabrication of PNCs that demonstrate simultaneous enhancement of multiple properties has been widely favored for development of structural and non-structural materials for various applications [19, 20]. In addition to its dependence on the composite constituents, electrical behavior of PNCs has been shown to be notably sensitive to alignment, distribution and dispersion of nanomaterials which can remarkably define the degree of anisotropy exhibited by a given PNC system [21-23]. The hypothesis is that advanced manufacturing methods such as SLS have technical advantages and can be used to fabricate PNCs that exhibit multifunctional performance by providing better control of the nanomaterial dispersion and alignment within the polymer.

In this work, the electrical conductivity measurements were performed through cross-sectional planes normal to the sintering plane and injection flow direction (in-plane) for “longitudinal” measurements (distance between contacts is 20-25 mm) along the direction schematically shown in Figure 1a. The ‘transverse’ resistance of the samples was separately characterized through the width (distance between contacts is 12-13 mm), and thickness (distance between contacts is 2-3 mm) which are mutually orthogonal to the longitudinal directions. Figure 1b and c represent the schematic configuration of the transverse measurements through the width and thickness of the specimens. In order to reduce the contact resistance and increase the contact surface between metal probes and samples, each pair of parallel cross sections corresponding to measurements through the desired direction was silver painted and air dried for at least 24 hours before measurements. The conductive paint on the sides of the samples was perfectly removed before performing measurements along other directions. No annealing for removal of thermal history was used in order to compare the neat effect of manufacturing method on the properties of interest and to avoid likely reconstruction or/and

destruction of the existing GNP networks. To obtain the true value of the conductivity of the PNCs, the measurements were performed on three samples and the average values were considered.

Figure 2a and 2b show the electrical conductivity of the PNCs with respect to measurement directions, the frequency of the AC voltage and GNP concentration for the SLS and IM process, respectively. Figure 2a shows that the conductivity of the 5wt% SLS PNCs remains invariant within a greater range of AC frequencies than that observed from measurements along the width and thickness. However, 3wt% SLS made PNCs represent fairly identical trends irrespective of the directions investigated. As is seen in Figure 2b, IM processed PNCs exhibit similar trends with respect to the frequency range regardless of the GNP loading and measurement direction. It is clear that IM made PNCs do not exhibit enhanced electrical performance and remain non-conductive along each direction. It is clearly demonstrated that i) PNCs made by SLS show greater conductivity along the length than the other directions and exhibit anisotropic electrical performance, and ii) 5wt% SLS processed PNCs have an electrical conductivity that is three orders of magnitude greater than that of the 3wt% PNCs along a given direction. However, the results are not conclusive to whether or not IM processed PNCs exhibit directionally dependent conductivity as the percolation threshold is higher than the 5 wt% of GNP which was the maximum GNP content used in the study.

The observations indicate that 5wt% GNP is above the onset of percolation threshold when SLS is used whereas it is apparent this loading is less than the percolation onset in case of IM process. The observed difference between the electrical conductivity behavior of SLS and IM made composites was correlated to the morphology and crystallization characteristics that are altered by the manufacturing techniques. The GNP-coated PA12 powder is sintered in absence of shear and/or elongational forces in SLS processing and thus the continuous GNP network formed during the coating method is maintained in the SLS processed PNCs.

Another factor that may affect the enhancement in electrical conductivity of PNCs is the degree of crystallinity [24, 25]. As reported in literature [26], the amorphous phase has been shown to enhance dispersion state and hence decrease the probability of formation of conductive networks within a semi-crystalline PNC system.

6 Morphology of Nanocomposites

SEM images of the fracture surface of 5wt% PNCs processed by IM and SLS are shown in Figure 3a and 3b, respectively. It is clearly seen that SLS resulted in GNP aggregates that seem to promote conductive GNP paths of nanomaterials. However, such networks are absent in case of IM processed composites that confirmed the non-conductive behavior of the IM made PNCs. Destruction of conductive networks induced by high shear forces during IM and/or re-agglomeration of GNP during the melt mixing process may explain the observed morphology of the IM PNCs as reported elsewhere [25, 27]. The observations also indicate presence of larger GNP phases in case of IM than SLS processed composites. The SEM images confirm the view that poorly dispersed GNP reduces the available interface between GNP and polymer and thus compromises the reinforcement efficiency of GNP in IM made nanocomposites which explains the observed elastic behavior of IM made PNCs.

7 Conclusions

The goal of this study was to examine the capability of SLS to fabricate PNCs with enhanced multifunctional performance. PNCs of GNP/PA12 were made using SLS and IM and characterized in terms of their mechanical, thermomechanical, thermal and electrical properties. The process-structure-property relationship was assessed to better understand the effect of sintering method on macro-scale properties of fabricated PNCs. It was demonstrated that SLS made parts yielded comparable or better tensile performance than IM processed parts. However, unlike IM, SLS negatively affected the impact resistance of the composites. In spite of the observed decrease in degree of crystallinity of PNCs with addition of GNP, composites exhibited monotonous decrease of $\tan\delta$ that was more pronounced in case of SLS. 5wt% GNP composites processed by SLS represented the best electrical conductivity suggesting that formation of conductive paths in IM composites are destroyed when IM is used whereas these networks are maintained after sintering the composite powder. Moreover, the results revealed that SLS made PNCs had directionally dependent electrical properties. The results supported the view that SLS has the potential to become a key industrial processing tool for fabrication of electrically conductive GNP/PA12 PNCs with enhanced mechanical performance.

References

- [1] Athreya SR, Kalaitzidou K, Das S "Processing and characterization of a carbon black-filled electrically conductive Nylon-12 nanocomposite produced by selective laser sintering". *Materials Science and Engineering: A*. Vol. 527, No. 10, pp 2637-2642, 2010.
- [2] Kim HC, Hahn HT, Yang YS "Synthesis of PA12/functionalized GNP nanocomposite powders for the selective laser sintering process". *Journal of composite materials*. Vol. No. pp 2012.
- [3] Chung H, Das S "Functionally graded Nylon-11/silica nanocomposites produced by selective laser sintering". *Materials Science and Engineering: A*. Vol. 487, No. 1, pp 251-257, 2008.
- [4] Goodridge R, Shofner M, Hague R, McClelland M, Schlea M, Johnson R, Tuck C "Processing of a Polyamide-12/carbon nanofibre composite by laser sintering". *Polymer Testing*. Vol. 30, No. 1, pp 94-100, 2011.
- [5] Kim J, Creasy T "Selective laser sintering characteristics of nylon 6/clay-reinforced nanocomposite". *Polymer Testing*. Vol. 23, No. 6, pp 629-636, 2004.
- [6] Athreya SR, Kalaitzidou K, Das S "Mechanical and microstructural properties of Nylon-12/carbon black composites: Selective laser sintering versus melt compounding and injection molding". *Composites Science and Technology*. Vol. 71, No. 4, pp 506-510, 2011.
- [7] Chung H, Das S "Processing and properties of glass bead particulate-filled functionally graded Nylon-11 composites produced by selective laser sintering". *Materials Science and Engineering: A*. Vol. 437, No. 2, pp 226-234, 2006.
- [8] Goodridge R, Tuck C, Hague R "Laser sintering of polyamides and other polymers". *Progress in Materials Science*. Vol. 57, No. 2, pp 229-267, 2012.
- [9] Athreya SR, Kalaitzidou K, Das S "Microstructure, thermomechanical properties, and electrical conductivity of carbon black - filled nylon - 12 nanocomposites prepared by selective laser sintering". *Polymer Engineering & Science*. Vol. 52, No. 1, pp 12-20, 2011.
- [10] Petrović ZS, Javni I, Waddon A, Bánhegyi G "Structure and properties of polyurethane-silica nanocomposites". *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*. Vol. 76, No. 2, pp 133-151, 2000.
- [11] Kalaitzidou K, Fukushima H, Drzal LT "A new compounding method for exfoliated graphite-polypropylene nanocomposites with enhanced flexural properties and lower percolation threshold". *Composites Science and Technology*. Vol. 67, No. 10, pp 2045-2051, 2007.
- [12] Kalaitzidou K, Fukushima H, Miyagawa H, Drzal LT "Flexural and tensile moduli of polypropylene nanocomposites and comparison of experimental data to Halpin - Tsai and Tandon - Weng models". *Polymer Engineering & Science*. Vol. 47, No. 11, pp 1796-1803, 2007.

- [13] Phang IY, Liu T, Mohamed A, Pramoda KP, Chen L, Shen L, Chow SY, He C, Lu X, Hu X "Morphology, thermal and mechanical properties of nylon 12/organoclay nanocomposites prepared by melt compounding". *Polymer international*. Vol. 54, No. 2, pp 456-464, 2004.
- [14] Cho J, Paul D "Nylon 6 nanocomposites by melt compounding". *Polymer*. Vol. 42, No. 3, pp 1083-1094, 2001.
- [15] Zhao F, Bao X, McLauchlin AR, Gu J, Wan C, Kandasubramanian B "Effect of POSS on morphology and mechanical properties of polyamide 12/montmorillonite nanocomposites". *Applied Clay Science*. Vol. 47, No. 3, pp 249-256, 2010.
- [16] Sargsyan A, Tonoyan A, Davtyan S, Schick C "The amount of immobilized polymer in PMMA SiO₂ nanocomposites determined from calorimetric data". *European Polymer Journal*. Vol. 43, No. 8, pp 3113-3127, 2007.
- [17] Zhang X, Loo LS "Study of glass transition and reinforcement mechanism in polymer/layered silicate nanocomposites". *Macromolecules*. Vol. 42, No. 14, pp 5196-5207, 2009.
- [18] Goertzen WK, Kessler M "Dynamic mechanical analysis of fumed silica/cyanate ester nanocomposites". *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. Vol. 39, No. 5, pp 761-768, 2008.
- [19] Hu N, Masuda Z, Yan C, Yamamoto G, Fukunaga H, Hashida T "The electrical properties of polymer nanocomposites with carbon nanotube fillers". *Nanotechnology*. Vol. 19, No. 21, pp 215701, 2008.
- [20] Sengupta R, Bhattacharya M, Bandyopadhyay S, Bhowmick AK "A review on the mechanical and electrical properties of graphite and modified graphite reinforced polymer composites". *Progress in polymer science*. Vol. 36, No. 5, pp 638-670, 2011.
- [21] Du F, Scogna RC, Zhou W, Brand S, Fischer JE, Winey KI "Nanotube networks in polymer nanocomposites: rheology and electrical conductivity". *Macromolecules*. Vol. 37, No. 24, pp 9048-9055, 2004.
- [22] Jing X, Zhao W, Lan L "The effect of particle size on electric conducting percolation threshold in polymer/conducting particle composites". *Journal of materials science letters*. Vol. 19, No. 5, pp 377-379, 2000.
- [23] Ramasubramaniam R, Chen J, Liu H "Homogeneous carbon nanotube/polymer composites for electrical applications". *Applied Physics Letters*. Vol. 83, No. pp 2928, 2003.
- [24] Chodak I, Krupa I "“Percolation effect” and mechanical behavior of carbon black filled polyethylene". *Journal of materials science letters*. Vol. 18, No. 18, pp 1457-1459, 1999.
- [25] Kalaitzidou K, Fukushima H, Askeland P, Drzal LT "The nucleating effect of exfoliated graphite nanoplatelets and their influence on the crystal structure and electrical conductivity of polypropylene nanocomposites". *Journal of materials science*. Vol. 43, No. 8, pp 2895-2907, 2008.
- [26] Tjong S, Liang G, Bao S "Effects of crystallization on dispersion of carbon nanofibers and electrical properties of polymer nanocomposites". *Polymer Engineering & Science*. Vol. 48, No. 1, pp 177-183, 2008.
- [27] Lanticse LJ, Tanabe Y, Matsui K, Kaburagi Y, Suda K, Hoteida M, Endo M, Yasuda E "Shear-induced preferential alignment of carbon nanotubes resulted in anisotropic electrical conductivity of polymer composites". *Carbon*. Vol. 44, No. 14, pp 3078-3086, 2006.

Fig. 1. Measurement directions used to determine electrical resistance of the SLS and IM processed specimens through (a) longitudinal (in-plane) and transverse direction through (b) the width and (c) thickness of specimens

Fig. 2. Electrical conductivity of the PNCs with respect to measurement direction for a) SLS and b) IM process as a function of the frequency of the AC voltage and GNP concentration

Fig. 3. Fracture surface of 5wt% GNP/PA12 composites made by a) IM and b) SLS indicating presence of well dispersed GNP in case of IM processed PNCs and GNP aggregated phase promoting formation of GNP conductive networks in SLS made PNCs

Table 1. Dependence of tensile properties and impact strength of GNP/PA12 composites on manufacturing method and GNP content

Sample	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Impact strength (J/m)
PA-IM	1.2±0.1	40.6±0.5	33.9±1.2
PA-SLS	1.5±0.1	42.8±0.7	40.9±4.4
3GNP/PA-IM	1.5±0.1	43.9±1.1	47.6±3.7
3GNP/PA-SLS	1.5±0.1	45.2±1.9	32.6±2.2
5GNP/PA-IM	2.2±0.1	44.3±2.8	23.5±0.7
5GNP/PA-SLS	1.6±0.1	45.6±2.1	20.3±0.7

Table 2. Effect of manufacturing method and GNP content on heat of fusion, degree of crystallinity, T_g and tanδ of GNP/PA12 composites

Sample	ΔH _f (J/g)	χ%	T _g (°C)	tanδ @ T _g
PA-IM	61.21±0.22	29.25±0.10	50.9±0.8	0.119
PA-SLS	76.18±3.02	36.42±1.44	55.8±0.5	0.114
3GNP/PA-IM	49.60±0.38	24.44±0.18	53.6±0.7	0.105
3GNP/PA-SLS	56.60±0.72	27.89±0.35	55.3±0.2	0.093
5GNP/PA-IM	48.62±0.10	24.46±0.05	53.6±0.5	0.076
5GNP/PA-SLS	47.88±1.40	24.10±0.70	56.3±0.3	0.072